

A Cross-Sectional Study of the Association of Body Mass Index and Physical Fitness Index of College Students in India

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Abstract:

Introduction: This study examines the relationship between Body Mass Index (BMI) and Physical Fitness Index (PFI) among Indian college students, highlighting how body composition influences physical fitness.

Methodology: A cross-sectional analysis was conducted with 198 students from Patna Medical College, India, over the academic year 2022-2023. BMI and PFI measurements were taken twice, and statistical analyses included Pearson's correlation and regression models.

Results: Results showed a moderate inverse correlation between BMI and PFI, especially in obese ($r = -0.45$) and underweight ($r = -0.32$) individuals, despite most students falling within the normal BMI range.

Conclusion: Extremes in BMI correlate with reduced physical fitness among college students. Optimal BMI maintenance is crucial for enhancing physical fitness.

Recommendation: Institutions should implement health programs promoting balanced diets and physical activity to improve student fitness levels.

Keywords: Body Mass Index, Physical Fitness Index, College Students, India, Health Interventions.

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Introduction

The influence of physical fitness on health outcomes has been extensively documented in scientific literature. [1] An important aspect of this exploration is understanding how body mass index (BMI) interacts with physical fitness levels among different populations. BMI is a simple index commonly used to classify underweight, overweight, and obesity in adults. It is calculated from an individual's weight and height and provides a gross measure of a person's tissue mass. [2] However, its relationship with physical fitness, especially among younger adults such as college students, remains underexplored in the context of developing nations like India. [3]

India, with its vast and diverse population, presents a unique demographic for studying health metrics. Indian college students represent a particularly interesting cohort due to their transitional phase of life, which often includes significant changes in lifestyle, dietary habits, and physical activity levels. [4] These changes can affect both BMI and overall physical fitness, making this group a prime subject for such studies. Physical fitness, generally assessed through various components including cardiovascular endurance, muscle strength, flexibility, and body composition, is crucial for overall health and well-being. [5,6] It is influenced

by numerous factors including regular physical activity, diet, genetics, and lifestyle choices. The interaction between BMI and physical fitness can offer insights into potential health risks or benefits and guide interventions aimed at improving health outcomes in this population. [7]

The study's focus on the cross-sectional association between BMI and the Physical Fitness Index (PFI) among college students in India is timely and relevant. [8] It seeks to fill the gap in the literature regarding the physical health metrics of young adults in a rapidly developing country, where changes in lifestyle and health behaviors are continuously evolving. Moreover, investigating this association can provide foundational data that may influence public health policies and individual lifestyle choices among the youth in India. [9]

The primary aim of this study is to examine the association between Body Mass Index (BMI) and Physical Fitness Index (PFI) among college students in India. [10] This will involve identifying patterns and correlations between BMI categories and various components of physical fitness, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of how body composition impacts this demographic's physical health and fitness levels. [11,12]

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional analysis designed to evaluate the association between Body Mass Index (BMI) and Physical Fitness Index (PFI) among college students in India. The design allows for a snapshot of data to be collected at a single point in time, providing a clear picture of the current status and correlations between BMI and physical fitness within the population of interest.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College, a higher education institution located in India. The data collection phase spanned one academic year, from January 2022 to December 2023, incorporating both academic and vacation periods to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the students' typical physical fitness and BMI throughout the year.

Participants: A total of 198 college students participated in the study. These participants were selected through a stratified sampling method to ensure representation across various faculties and years of study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Enrolled full-time in Patna Medical College.
- Aged between 18 to 25 years.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Students with any medical condition affecting mobility or diet.
- Students who were pregnant during the period of the study.

Bias: To minimize bias, the study ensured a randomized selection of participants from each department within the college. Data analysts were blinded to the identities of the participants to prevent any subjective influence on the data interpretation. Efforts were made to standardize all measurements across different times and settings.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data on BMI was collected using a standardized protocol where height and weight were measured using calibrated scales and stadiometers. Physical fitness was assessed using the Physical Fitness Index, which includes tests for cardiovascular endurance, muscle strength, flexibility, and body composition.

The data were collected in two sessions per participant - one at the start and another at the end of the academic year - to account for any seasonal variations in physical activity and fitness levels. The data collection team consisted of trained healthcare professionals and fitness experts to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the study population in terms of age, gender, BMI categories, and PFI scores. The association between BMI and PFI was analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient to explore the strength and direction of the relationship. Multivariable regression models were employed to adjust for potential confounders such as age, gender, and dietary habits. All analyses were performed using SPSS software, with a p-value of less than 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Participant Characteristics

Characteristic	Total Participants (N=198)
Age (years)	
Mean (SD)	21.4 (2.1)
Gender	
Male	102 (51.5%)
Female	96 (48.5%)
BMI Category	
Underweight (<18.5)	30 (15.2%)
Normal (18.5-24.9)	112 (56.6%)
Overweight (25-29.9)	36 (18.2%)
Obese (≥30)	20 (10.1%)
Physical Fitness Index (PFI)	
Low (<30)	22 (11.1%)
Moderate (30-50)	88 (44.4%)
High (>50)	88 (44.4%)

Table 2: Correlation between BMI and Physical Fitness Index (PFI)

BMI Category	Mean PFI Score	Pearson Correlation Coefficient
Underweight	45.2	-0.32
Normal	50.6	-
Overweight	42.7	-0.28
Obese	35.9	-0.45

The results presented in Table 1 indicate a balanced distribution of gender among the participants with a slight majority of males (51.5%). The average age of participants was 21.4 years, reflecting the typical college age group. The distribution of BMI categories shows that the majority of students fall within the normal range (56.6%), while a notable proportion are either overweight (18.2%) or obese (10.1%).

Table 2 reveals a negative correlation between BMI and PFI across different BMI categories. The Pearson correlation coefficients suggest a moderate inverse relationship, particularly pronounced in the obese category ($r = -0.45$), indicating that higher BMI is associated with lower physical fitness levels. Among the underweight category, the correlation coefficient was -0.32 , suggesting that very low BMI could also be associated with lower physical fitness, though to a lesser extent compared to the obese group. The normal BMI group did not exhibit a significant correlation, which might suggest a stable physical fitness level across this group.

These findings underscore the potential impact of BMI extremes on physical fitness among college students. The negative correlation observed, particularly among overweight and obese participants, highlights the need for targeted health and fitness programs to improve or maintain physical fitness levels in this population.

Discussion

The study revealed a moderate inverse correlation between BMI and Physical Fitness Index (PFI) among college students, particularly pronounced in individuals classified as obese and underweight. [13,14] The majority of students fell within the normal BMI range, yet significant proportions were found in the overweight and obese categories. The findings indicate that BMI extremes are associated with lower physical fitness levels. [15] The inverse relationship between BMI and PFI suggests that as BMI increases beyond the normal range, physical fitness levels tend to decrease. This pattern is particularly strong in obese individuals, where a higher BMI is likely linked to reduced cardiovascular fitness, lower muscle strength, and flexibility. [16] Similarly, the underweight group, though less affected than the obese group, showed a negative correlation, suggesting that very low body mass may also impair physical fitness, potentially due to inadequate muscle mass and nutritional deficiencies. [17]

Previous studies have consistently shown that an optimal BMI is crucial for maintaining good physical health and fitness. Research in various global contexts points to the detrimental effects of high BMI on physical capabilities, especially cardiovascular health and musculoskeletal function.

However, the specific impact on Indian college students has been less frequently explored. [18] Compared to studies from other regions, the findings from this study align with the global narrative but highlight a critical concern within this demographic that mirrors a worldwide trend. The observed trends in this study can be explained through the physiological impacts of excess body weight on bodily functions. High BMI, often resulting from increased fat accumulation, imposes greater strain on the heart, joints, and muscles, thereby hindering physical performance. [19] Conversely, underweight individuals might lack the necessary muscle mass or energy reserves to perform optimally in physical activities. The patterns observed in the normal BMI category, showing no significant correlation, suggest that within this range, factors other than BMI might play more pivotal roles in determining physical fitness, such as genetics, diet, and lifestyle choices. [20]

This study contributes to a deeper understanding of the health dynamics within the Indian collegiate context and underscores the need for holistic health interventions tailored to address the specific needs of this population. Such interventions should not only focus on promoting optimal BMI but also on enhancing overall physical fitness through targeted exercise programs and nutritional guidance.

Conclusion

This study highlighted a significant inverse correlation between BMI and Physical Fitness Index (PFI) among college students in India, particularly noting pronounced effects in individuals with BMI classifications at the extremes—obese and underweight. These findings underline the crucial impact of maintaining an optimal BMI for better physical fitness outcomes. While the majority of students fell within the normal BMI range, the presence of a considerable number in the overweight and obese categories emphasizes the need for targeted health interventions. These interventions should not only aim to moderate BMI through a balanced diet and regular physical activity but also enhance overall physical fitness, thus potentially improving health outcomes for this young adult population. This research contributes valuable insights into the interaction between body composition and physical fitness, offering a foundation for future health promotion strategies in educational institutions.

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